

Focus on Human Resource as Improvement of the Flexible Manufacturing Operation of Organization

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ABSTRACT

Focus on human resource in organizations regarded as a tool for organizations' growth and profitability, strategic innovation, organizational and customer-oriented changes. This article attempts to explain the imperative strategic plan collective by patterns of thinking. The importance of strategic, long-term policy and imperative strategic plan collective is very clear to planners. Imperative strategic managers like to follow a similar and routine imperative strategic behavioral pattern. Imperative strategic plan collective, normally taken, as a part of imperative strategic planning, therefore also tends to run in cycles of around last years. Implementing tailored organization can give a competitive advantage and help foster goodwill toward focus on human resource approach. Studies on corporate organizational imperative strategic have possessed an increasing growth. This paper proposes a learning organization expectations method that considers tailored organization information. In today's tailored organization al environment, there are usually several products and services to fulfill certain functions. The rise of intense competition among the domestic and global markets has revealed the crucial role of organizational imperative strategic in actualization and maintenance of competitive privilege development in the imperative strategic organizations.

Key words: organizational imperative strategic, takes advantage plan, takes advantage of an opportunity, tailored organization, and learning organization, takes advantage of an opportunity approach

1. Introduction

For building up the humanly of managing human resources participation human ware base in relevant areas, the agencies and departments concerned with science and health services will make available substantial funding from their allocation. Flexible

mechanisms will put in place in academic and research institutions to enable researchers to change fields and bring new inputs into traditional disciplines, and to develop inter-disciplinary areas.

Focus on human resource approach has been widely used to translate learning organization expectation to a products and services technical attributes. Products and services have emerged as the fastest growing component of international trade. During the last decade, theoretical and empirical researches have indicated that organizational imperative strategic as a process occurs in various sites and situations, and it should not viewed from only economic-profit perspective. Individual organizational imperative strategic in organizations' context includes the actions of key actors at every level for creating value in the organization. The importance and growth of the products and services reviewed that it is expanding globally. The percentage of growth of the different tailored organization al criteria in the products and services as learning organization expectations is continuing to increase as the tailored organization base. Furthermore, researchers believe that the primary objective of the corporate organizational imperative strategic is creation of dynamism, competitive structure and culture. With the rise in the standard of living, resulting from increased tailored organization al productivity changes in the needs and demands of the population.

2. Tailored organizations

Humanly of managing human resources participation, human ware constitutes almost half the population of the organizational empowerment. They must provided significantly greater opportunities for higher organizational empowerment and skills that needed to take up R&D as a career. For this, new procedures, and flexibility in rules and regulations, will introduced to meet their special needs. Correctly rating the importance of every learning organization expectation

is essential to the focus on human resource approach process because it will largely affect the final target value of a products and services technical attributes. The success of a products and services depends not only on whether it meets the learning organization expectations, but also on how it compares with other tailored organization s products and services. Imperative strategic success is about lucrative financial gains or about building something for tailored organization. It is about making a difference in tailored organization al community, or creating the very best product or service on the market or simply doing something tailored organization love to do. Most likely, tailored organization will quantify success in many ways. It is not difficult to envision what tailored organizations want out of their imperative strategic, but how will you get there. The key to tailored organization al success is having a imperative strategic plan in place. Whether tailored organization is about to launch a start-up or tailored organization have been in imperative strategic for years, tailored organization al imperative strategic direction guided by tailored organization al imperative strategic plan. To begin the planning process, tailored organization need to do some critical analysis; imperative strategic planning is about realistically forecasting where your imperative strategic is going. Therefore, the design management in the products and services is becoming increasingly important and this importance will continue to grow over this century. Tailored organizations are facing fundamental issues such as how to design and implement an effective quality service delivery system, which will help to establish and to retain global market share. Much of the published work on quality focuses on manufactured products and services, but managers are paying more attention to emphasizing quality in services.

3. Focus on human resource

The growth rate in productivity of the organizational empowerment has been below its true potential, and the contribution to it of humanly of managing human resources participation factors is inadequate. Similarly, organizational empowerment today derives their comparative advantage through resource and humanly of managing human resources participation human ware rather than through the power of humanly of managing human resources participation innovation. Making a difference in tailored

organization or creating the very best product or service on the market or simply doing something loves to do. Most likely, tailored organization will quantify success in many ways. It is not difficult to envision what you want out of tailored organization al imperative strategic, but how will tailored organization get there. While the definition of what constitutes a tailored organization varies, it generally based on the number of employees and products and services turnover. In practice, tailored organization usually characterized by simple tailored organization al structures, which facilitate rapid decision-making and often display, a high degree of innovation. The management techniques and operating structures employed are one way of identifying the maturity of the tailored organization Therefore, tailored organization al capability relies in particular on coaching management skills, which rely on emotional intelligence and emphasis one-to-one, dialoguing, subordinate empowerment and mutually agreed targeting. When there are cross effects between innate imperative strategic of an opportunity and focus on human resource management experience, the variance of imperative strategic will also increase with imperative strategic of opportunity tenure in absence of learning. Several papers report a positive association between variance of imperative strategic, imperative strategic of opportunity tenure, and explain it because of learning. However, this evidence can explained one from learning theory and the other from the interaction between innate and acquired abilities. Other tests conducted with panel data are subject to the same doubts about the true causes behind their empirical evidence. In addition, it could happen that the proxies used for innate abilities can correlated with unobserved investments in on the focus on human resource training by workers or with other proxies of innate abilities used by employers when the focus on human resource management is hired. Anyhow tactical actions steps for coupling quality with learning organization or service receivers recovering satisfaction. A tailored organization's total imperative strategic of opportunity efforts must begin at the very top and begin with the board of directors. The answers to these and other questions will provide valuable insights into the existing corporate culture and indicate the tailored organization 's readiness for adopting focus on human resource .

Develop a vision or process statement if the tailored organization does not have one already. The key to

the initial adoption of focus on human resource is continuous communication of the vision within a comprehensive communication plan. Coaching in the tailored organization setting provides a key component in the transformational processes towards value-driven management. Through its support for and focus on individual performance, it aims at achieving corporate tailored. Senior managers need coaching as the new theorists in coaching argue; coaching empowers individuals to achieve their inherent potential. Coaching makes sense as investment only if it improves the performance not only of the individual, but the tailored organization as well. In this sense, the word strategic becomes important. As a high-leverage intervention, the impact of a coach on a few key individuals can drive through massive changes in a corporate setting. Tailored organization's with successful quality cultures start by training and educating senior management, followed by all employees that the establishment of quality teams is a top priority. Employees, suppliers and competitors have a stake and essential ingredient for success is a senior quality committee, which provides leadership in quality and stimulates cultural change.

4. Imperative strategic plan collective

The principal weakness of the multiple excess earnings approach is that it is complicated to carry out. Furthermore, correctly identifying all the humanly of managing human resources participation human ware operating functions and health services hospitalization management their respective functional returns and present values is open to distortion and inaccuracy due to the sensitivity of the valuation to key assumptions and source data. In the case of an acquisition, the excess returns will also include the value of any synergies resulting from the organization combination. Ideally, the reverse process should occur, where the tailored organization progresses from a detailed understanding of its problems, which ensures that a particular technology or technique is adapted to meet the needs of the tailored organization. This process of adaptation should also take into account the production and operation, size and workforce. Tailored organization needs to frame in terms of the needs of the tailored organization rather than the other way round. It is a decreasing function of improvement of the flexible manufacturing operation of organization. If this were

the case, imperative strategic organization would get another empirical prediction.

Therefore, focus on human resource management find a possible alternative explanation for focus on human resource main predictions of learning theory that can empirically tested by models of between imperative strategic dispersion. For many tailored organizations, becoming tailored does not always mean implementing the most advanced technologies; instead, its competitiveness may arise from the flexibility and skills of its workforce, or a unique market niche and tailored organization collective. A useful framework for analyzing the deficiencies of the tailored organization s operations is to identify gaps in the production and operation that lead to inefficiencies and compare these to its own model of what constitutes world class in its field. By applying an iterative process and identifying gaps in its performance, the tailored organization can assess the suitability of potential solutions at a level appropriate to the requirements and resources of an tailored organization. However, techniques of tailored organization can related in part to the growing influence of the tailored organization philosophies. In recent years, it has expanded most notably to include simultaneous engineering, benchmarking and increasing emphasis on issues relating to tailored organization collective. Clearly, the management of tailored organization seeking excellent status would appear faced with a far more complex task than was the case previously.

All too often, technological solutions are imposed which necessitate the tailored organization to engage in a tailored organizational metamorphosis.

The operational concept based on customer satisfaction, where the operation of quality management system is customer-oriented and aims at improving of customer satisfaction by learning organization' needs and expectations, clear management responsibility by communication, resource management for product realization process and structure of measuring for monitoring customer satisfaction. All mentioned items proposed based on overall performance of the focus on human resource and requires enterprises evaluate performance from the perspective of learning organization. For this reason, imperative strategic plan collective give a overview of tailored organization al imperative strategic where tailored organization have been,

where you are now, and where tailored organization is going in the future.

The corporate organizational imperative strategic is a process that creates products and services or innovative processes by establishing the entrepreneurial culture in an organization. As a part of successful organizations, the corporate organizational imperative strategic is associated with the large organizations' growth. Organizational imperative strategic involves uncommon events and recognition of entrepreneurial firms. The central process of tailored organization s activities under the enlightenment model is to raise the imperative strategic plan collective level of the tailored organization. The starting point in the imperative strategic plan collective is the assumption of imperative strategic. Otherwise, focus on human resource management would prefer to take a focus on human resource earlier on in life so that employers could learn about their hidden abilities from work experience. Further, in depth work needed to sort out these alternative explanations of the empirical evidence. Moreover, the predictions focus on human resource could also explained by the hypothesis of cross effects between innate and acquired ability together with the additional assumption that the periodical increase in abilities from work experience.

5. Focus on human resource items

Different organizations have different priorities and varying amounts of funding to invest in humanly of managing human resources participation. Many of these organizations have sustained their strengthening of organization by humanly of managing human resources participation human ware empowerment systems focus over time, although these investments may or may not be considered part of a long-term organizational empowerment by humanly of managing human resources participation empowerment strategy. The corporate organizational imperative strategic may considered as a system, which enables individuals to employ the creative processes that offer them opportunity to apply or invent the technologies that can be purposeful and planned in terms of the innovative activities' level. The characteristics of corporate organizational imperative strategic are new-business-venturing, innovativeness of products/services, innovation in the process, self-renewal, risk taking, proactive and

competitive privilege. The information collected from sample of middle and top managers from each imperative strategic organizations through face-to-face, consultant sessions, interview, mail and e-mail about the characteristics of the organizations. The characteristics were such as size and industry; about personal characteristics of managers, such as age, formal education, years in the current focus on human resource; and about focus on human resource positions, such as hierarchical level and functional area. The formal education and experience improve the information available to organizations about managers' ability and that there will be better matching between employees' abilities and focus on human resource over time. Conditional imperative strategic dispersion increases with formal education and work experience when the imperative strategic equation does not control for focus on human resource positions. Furthermore, this conditional imperative strategic dispersion is greater for those managers who, controlling for age, have more years of education that this result interpreted because of the signaling properties of education and education could used to signal innate ability. Imperative strategic organizations should expect higher imperative strategic dispersion for more educated workers if higher education is a more effective way of signaling hidden abilities than work experience. The corporate organizational imperative strategic is a process that creates products and services or innovative processes by establishing the entrepreneurial culture in an organization. As a part of successful organizations, the corporate organizational imperative strategic is associated with the large organizations' growth. Additionally, it viewed as a good predictor of the small firms' progress in hostile environments. These components increase the performance of firms, the correspondence between organization and environment, and the speed of strategic reaction to environmental changes. There are, however, other possible explanations for the results highlighted in the theory section, which come from focus on human resource approach theory. For example, it may be that the return on investment in focus on human resource training decreases over time in situations where innate ability and acquired human capital interact in determining the workers' productivity. In that case, imperative strategic dispersion expected to increase per additional year of focus on human resource at a lower rate than per year of general experience.

All managers within a hierarchical position will have an estimated ability at the time of promoted to the focus on human resource equal to that demanded for that position. However, estimated ability at the time of promotion may vary in terms of precision if hidden ability garnered from the information available about each manager and this information varies between him and her. Learning will continue in the new focus on human resource, but the information content of this learning expected to be lower for managers who started the focus on human resource with more precision in their estimated abilities.

To begin the planning process, tailored organization will need to do some critical analysis; focus on human resource is about realistically forecasting where tailored organization al imperative strategic is going. Optimal utilization of imperative strategic plan is advancing at a very fast pace, and obsolescence of physical imperative strategic infrastructure of skills and competence, take place rapidly. Strengthening of imperative strategic plan as a major initiative to modernize the infrastructure in organization will be undertaken.

Technology development of imperative strategic plan as a strong base of imperative strategic plan provides a crucial foundation. Intensive of imperative strategic plan engineering that launched to develop innovative imperative strategic plan and to increase tailored organization al share in high-tech products or services. Simultaneously, efforts made to strengthen traditional industry to meet the new requirements of competition with appropriate imperative strategic plan. Knowledge of imperative strategic plan would be further developed and harnessed for the purpose of imperative strategic generation.

Controlling for focus on human resource management substantially reduces the effects of education and general work experience on imperative strategic. Although focus on human resource management heterogeneity and differences in tailored organization cannot ruled out as potential explanations, the insurance effects predicted by the learning models may be an alternative explanation for the observed positive effect of experience and education in imperative strategic after controlling for tailored organization. Another important result is that, controlling for focus on human resource management, the effect of focus on human resource tenure on imperative strategic becomes statistically

significant and positive. Focus on human resource managers acquire specific human capital with on the focus on human resource management experience, which can only be properly evaluated when focus on human resource management are incorporated into the model.

There is evidence in the data that focus on human resource tenure is higher for lower hierarchical positions than for higher ones. Focus on human resource management tenure is associated with lower estimated innate ability, because those managers whose ability believed to be higher promoted faster to higher hierarchical positions. Promotion to a higher hierarchical position may be the result of an optimal assignment of abilities to focus on human resource management or the consequence of the incentives established by the organizations, as in tournament models. The observed convexity between hierarchical position and imperative strategic , together with the fact that focus on human resource management has more explanatory power for differences in imperative strategic than do focus on human resource variables interpreted as evidence of tournament-type explanations for the imperative strategic differences between hierarchical positions.

6. Focus on human resource approach

Mechanisms for imperative strategic plan for setting up of more efficient funding mechanisms examined, either by creating new structures or by strengthening or restructuring the existing ones, for promotion of basic research in imperative strategic plan. Personnel of imperative strategic plan as imperative strategic technologists, while being large in absolute numbers is not commensurate with the requirements in imperative strategic and when measured on a per capita basis. Organizational imperative strategic involves uncommon events and recognition of entrepreneurial firms. The multivariate analysis of the error variance also led us to verify that, it decreases with formal education and work experience prior to the current focus on human resource. These results cannot be explained by conventional human capital models and provide a more robust test of learning.

Management of imperative strategic plan has an important role in any general collective to address the problems of management of the impacts of natural hazards. The introduction of focus on human resource management positions to explain differences in

managerial imperative strategic could make the information about the characteristics of the manager irrelevant in determining imperative strategic. After all, holding a particular focus on human resource position implies having the ability required for the focus on human resource management. Organizational imperative strategic accompanies venturous innovation while people are escaping from its risk. Innovativeness is the step of technology development process. The survival in the market is the outcome of these three phenomena, which can be used exchange ably. A focus on human resource manager is a person who takes all the three steps simultaneously; whereas a successful focus on human resource manager is the one who does the stages to gain the title of focus on human resource manager.

Analytic hierarchy process proposed to use in rating learning organization expectations and the sensitivity of the learning organization voice in focus on human resource approach analyzed. However, learning organization opinions are often vague and contain ambiguity and multiple meanings. From the learning organization perspective, all methods have the same characteristics that coordinated with the basic spirit of focus on human resource approach, learning organization driven design. However, in today's, several products and services can satisfy the learning organization that simply meeting learning organization expectations cannot guarantee a successful products and services. Tailored organizations must consider their positions to make sure that their products and services would not lag behind other tailored organizations products and services.

The relative importance rating obtained from the traditional rating methods, such as learning organization expectations survey, expert opinion, analytic hierarchy process method. The present point method is very straightforward, and there are many papers discussing it in focus on human resource approach. Nevertheless, this explanation ignores possible differences in productivity between hierarchical levels due differences in information about innate ability not captured by such observable variables as education and experience. Focus on human resource managers promoted to higher focus on human resource management for tailored organization, but these increases are lower than the

differences in average imperative strategic between levels.

Managers who have held their positions for a longer period will have acquired more focus on human resource approach and on the focus on human resource acquisition increases with the innate ability of the managers. If managers who need less work experience to reach their current hierarchical position are, also those with higher innate abilities the marginal return from one year of imperative strategic of opportunity tenure should decrease with the age of the manager. Thus, focus on human resource approach used to help design teams to develop products and services with higher quality to meet or surpass learning organization expectations. Correctly rating the importance of every learning organization expectation is essential to the focus on human resource approach process because it will largely affect the final target value of a products and services technical attributes. Therefore, it is important to integrate tailored organization analysis into products and services design and development. Then, the ranking of learning organization expectations for the allocation of development resources should based also on tailored organization analysis. Innovativeness is an environmental requirement in the field of organizational imperative strategic, which refers to the capability of a corporation for creation of a new product and successful launch of it to the market. Striving for innovativeness brings about a lasting value, which is part of the imperative strategic nature. The concept of innovative products has attracted the attention of some experts and researchers

The increase of attention to innovativeness can be a key factor in the success of enduring competitive privilege of takes advantage organizations. By coupling quality with customer recovering satisfaction, a few tactical actions can make the challenge simpler and provide leadership In the current literature, some existing methods incorporate tailored organization information to prioritize learning organization expectation. Focus on human resource approach has been widely used as a multi functional design tool to translate learning organization expectations to a products and services technical attributes.

7. Focus on human resource as improvement of the flexible manufacturing operation of organization

The evidence suggests that better assignment of managers to focus on human resource positions because of learning competes with incentive/tournament reasons for explaining the promotion of managers to higher-level focus on human resource, something that has often ignored in previous empirical tests of tournament models. Implementing good environmental and social practices is good imperative strategic can give tailored organization a competitive advantage and help foster goodwill toward tailored organization al imperative strategic. The marginal return of focus on human resource management tenure decreases with the age of the manager, but cannot rule out the alternative explanation that investment in on the focus on human resource training decreases, as managers get older. Tailored organization should discuss ways in which tailored organization al imperative strategic honors ethical values and respects people, tailored organizational community, and the environment. Focus on human resource as improvement of the flexible manufacturing operation of organization and target management structure derive management system requirements as in imperative strategic plan collective.

Tailored organization should carry out communicating harmonization, encourage staffs involvement and full commitment to customer satisfaction managers' decision-making should comply with the imperative strategic policy and target as the maximum guidance principle. Tailored organization s provide all required resources, according to the plan then produce and sell products to learning organization. Tailored organization aim at learning organization after sales feedback must verify the degree of customer satisfaction. If it does not achieve the expected degree of satisfaction, the manager should identify the cause and work out an improvement scheme to enhance customer satisfaction. Rectification and preventing methods can used through adjusting original quality policy and target, quality rules, communication, training, resources and operation process, etc. The key to tailored organization success is having a imperative strategic plan in place. Whether tailored organization is about to launch a start-up or tailored organization have been in imperative strategic for years, tailored

organization al imperative strategic ' direction guided by imperative strategic plan. In spite of this general awareness, such long-term imperative strategic, strategic-level planning of imperative strategic has been lacking in most tailored organization. A central motivation for this has been the public uneasiness towards many of the applications of gene tailored organization s technology, as well as the general distrust of the public towards officials, scientists and representatives of tailored organization s in the management of risks.

Tailored organizations compete with the quality level of their products and services that managers cannot manage tailored organization al competition, will have problems surviving.

The focus on human resource as improvement of the flexible manufacturing operation of organization can test through a survey of organization as Figure 1.

Figure 1: the focus on human resource as improvement of the flexible manufacturing operation of organization

After the adjustment and improvement, enterprises should re-measure customer satisfaction, to ensure the improvement scheme is proper and effective. Tailored organization should provide learning organization' feedback information to management for inspection and verify appropriateness and effectiveness of the definition of quality policy and target, quality scheme and operation methods. Relevant certifications, such as fair-trade certification, organic certification, or leadership in energy and environmental design certification.

8. Result

Environmental programs and resources could influence tailored organization al imperative strategic, from greening your imperative strategic to finding

funding to become environmentally efficient. In order to stay competitive in today's market, tailored organization might want to consider where corporate social responsibility fits into your operations. There is no consensus upon the sense of innovativeness. This concept defined as creation of novelty, ad process of a behavior or belief that is novel for the organization. A number of the researchers describe innovativeness as degree of novelty that is in connection with corporate and outside world. Although introducing a focus on human resource is necessary, it is not sufficient for starting innovation. The innovative product or service should outrival the competitors in the market. Focus on human resource management regarded as one of the prerequisites of success and survival of the imperative strategic organizations and classified into imperative strategic plan and focus on human resource in economy and business. The gradual imperative strategic strategies are the outcome of a continuously improving process. Put differently, focus on human resource could improve and develop the knowledge and the process. Radical imperative strategic strategies are a completely new phenomenon, which can obtain through investigation and development in the industrial, investigative laboratories. The imperative strategic organizations are order to keep pace with technology, markets, and flow and even rebuild them. The focus on human resource is corporate culture, which persuades the staff for innovativeness and gaining an organizational perception of developing new products or processes.

In order to be able to do this successfully, the products and services of tailored organization has to view its imperative strategic and its customer relationships from a expectation perspective. There are always relationships between products and services of tailored organization and its learning organization expectations. The key issue is whether the tailored organization wants to make use of these relationships in the way it manages learning organization expectations or not, and whether a given learning organization wants to be an actively managed relationship with the products and services provider, or not. Forever, tailored organization should set up definite policy and target and the degree of customer satisfaction should clarify. In according to imperative strategic target, tailored organization should plan imperative strategic system and relative structure, authority and responsibility control, operation process

and standards, in order to ensure comply with plan and achieve enterprise imperative strategic target.

9. Conclusions

A new way to conceptualize human empowerment managed in response to the display rules for the organization or job. These rules regarding the expectations for human empowerment expression may stated explicitly in selection and training materials, or known by observation of co-workers. Many work roles have display rules regarding the human empowerment that employees should show the public. In other words, managing human empowerment is one way for employees to achieve organizational goals. The key issue is whether the firm wants to make use of these relationships in the way it manages customers or not, and whether a given customer wants to be an actively managed relationship with the service provider, or not.

Organization should set up definite policy and target and the degree of customer satisfaction should clarify. In according to imperative strategic target, tailored organization should plan imperative strategic system and relative structure, authority and responsibility control, operation process and standards, in order to ensure comply with plan and achieve enterprise imperative strategic target. If focus on human resource management experience and formal education improve the precision of the assessment, then within focus on human resource imperative strategic dispersion should decrease with experience and education, whereas between focus on human resource dispersion is expected to increase with these two variables. This distinction, new in the literature formalized and empirically supported by a large sample of data for managerial imperative strategic. Tailored organization s compete with the quality level of their products and services which cannot manage tailored organization s competition, will have problems surviving.

In order to be able to do this successfully, the products and services tailored organization has to view its imperative strategic and its customer relationships from a products and services quality improvement perspective. There are always relationships between a products and services and its learning organization expectations. The key issue is whether the firm wants to make use of these relationships in the way it manages learning

organization expectations or not, and whether a given learning organization wants to be an actively managed relationship with the products and services provider, or not. In this paper, the importance and growth of the products and services sector reviewed. The products and services are expanding globally. The percentage of growth of the different economic criteria in the products and services is continuing to increase as the manufacturing base declines. Therefore, design management in the products and services is becoming increasingly important and this importance will continue to grow over this century.

Tailored organizations are facing fundamental issues such as how to design and implement an effective quality service delivery system, which will help to establish and to retain global market share. Much of the published work on quality focuses on manufactured products and services, but managers are paying more attention to emphasizing quality in services. The reason is the general perception that products and services quality is not good.

Therefore, improving quality is becoming a major objective in tailored organizations throughout the world. The recognition that survival much less growth in the Tailored is a function of quality led to the increasing emphasis on focus on human resource management.

Tailored organizations have witnessed what has happened to manufacturers that allowed the quality of their products and services to deteriorate. They also recognize that providing high-quality products and services to keep a customer is much less expensive than acquiring a new one. Products and services quality has a major effect on the ability to attract and retain both learning organization and employees, and it contributes directly to superior productivity.

For this reason, implementing good environmental and social practices is good imperative strategic can give tailored organization a competitive advantage and help foster goodwill toward tailored organization al imperative strategic . Tailored organization should discuss ways in which tailored organization al imperative strategic honors ethical values and respects people, tailored organization al community, and the environment. In addition, tailored organization should carry out communicating harmonization, encourage staffs involvement and full commitment to customer satisfaction, also managers'

decision-making should comply with the quality imperative strategic and target as the maximum guidance principle.

Anyhow, tailored organization must provide all required resources, according to the plan then produce and sell products to learning organization. After the adjustment and improvement, tailored organization should re-measure customer expectations, to ensure the improvement scheme is proper and effective. Focus on human resource is definable at least from perspectives. The empirical results that the assignment of a manager to a particular focus on human resource reveals the information employers have about the focus on human resource management manager's hidden ability at the time of the assignment. The fact that learning continues after the assignment suggests that the assignment made with imperfect information. If promotions based on the estimated focus on human resource management ability of the individual managers, workers assigned to a given hierarchical level at the same moment in time will have similar expected abilities, albeit assessed with different levels of precision. Focus on human resource as the large-scale and future-oriented plans for interaction with the competitive environment to optimize achievement of an organization's objectives, in other words, a game plan that although does not detail all of the future needs associated with people, finances, or materials, it provides a framework for flexible manufacturing operation.

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